

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF THE PRESCHOOLER IN THE PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Ibragimova Odina Kamoldinovna

Andijan State University, General psychology
lecturer of the department

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ABSTRACT

The state reflects the individual psychological characteristics of preschoolers. The problem of social and psychological adaptation of preschoolers to the educational process is discussed in detail. Comprehensive measures that contribute to the socio-psychological adaptation of the organization of training for preschoolers should include methods and conditions for implementation, taking into account the age characteristics of children.

The adaptation process takes different time depending on the situation in which a person needs to adapt and his individual characteristics. No, as a result of social and psychological adaptation of a person always: he coordinates his goals with the values of society, it is taken into account to live safely with other people, to show initiative, to plan a future solution, new knowledge, skills, opportunities and abilities develop, establishing close, emotionally intense and long-term relationships with others. Mission accomplished. As a result of socio-psychological adaptation to the organization of additional education, the preschool educator learns and successfully works out forms of behavior, social norms, knowledge, values [1]. Today, the socio-psychological adaptation of a preschooler is determined by his all-round development

as a person capable of activity, focused on the modern system of values. Social adaptation in society and independent choice of lifestyle, self-development and self-improvement. Practice shows that basic education alone cannot provide this, therefore the formalization of preschool education requires additional education, which determines the inclinations, interests and opportunities. decisive factors in identification. [7].

The problems of socio-psychological adaptation are associated with getting into a new environment for a person and are traditionally considered both in sociology and in psychology. The study of this phenomenon in the domestic psychology of K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, L.S. Vygotsky, A.V. Zaporozhets, S.L. Rubinstein and others; in foreign psychology - J.G. Mead, M. Montessori, E. Thorndike, R. Steiner, E.

Erickson and others. Socio-psychological adaptation as an adaptation of a person to the social environment A. A. Rean, T. Parsons, J. Piaget and others. Other psychological mechanisms of adaptation analyzed in the works of B.N. Almazov, S.P. Ivanenkova, A.B. Petrovsky, A.A. Reana et al. B.G. Ananyeva, D.A. Andreeva, T.A. Golubeva et al. Individual adaptation mechanisms of Kh.A. Considered in the works of Bernstein, L.I. Bershedova, G. Selye. Personal and socio-psychological aspects of adaptation A. Bandura, A.A. Nachaldzhyan, K. Halla et al. Numerous researches - Wenger LA, Lisina EA, LA Yasyukova and others - dedicated to the adaptation of children to the conditions of preschool education. The role of the family in the social adaptation of the individual, in particular Yu.R. Vishnevsky, Ya. V. Didkovskaya, G. Simonova, T. Shilova. Modern studies of the social and psychological adaptation of children with disabilities L.I. Plaksina, O. G. Prikhodko, N. Ya. Semago, L. I. Solntseva, M. S. Staroverov and others [3].

The experience of psychologists, teachers and other specialists involved in the education system shows that the social experience of children with disabilities has ended, which is reflected in their behavioral reactions, low culture of communication, inadequate expression and perception of emotions. Normally developing children, in turn, also have personality traits that often misunderstand and misinterpret the behavior, needs and emotional makeup of a child with a disability. In this regard, conflicts arise between children, an uncomfortable psychological and emotional environment is observed in the group [4].

However, the accumulated experience of theoretical and empirical studies of the socio-psychological adaptation of preschool children with disabilities has not yet been sufficiently analyzed from the point of view of its specificity for inclusive groups with children of different levels of physical and mental health. may be. The available scientific material must be supplemented, generalized, systematized.

The system of methods of socio-psychological adaptation includes methods used when performing functional procedures of a preschool institution. In particular, the following methods can be used in the adaptation process: a universal method of information and consultation dialogue; new skills, behaviors and methods of stimulating and supporting the social environment used in social prevention; the method of fairy-tale therapy, related to the methods of social adaptation, is also used as adaptation trainings, personal social patronage, etc. [5]. Who are you for In practice, the continuing education teacher uses a variety of methods. The method of stimulating action and motivation is a means of internal and external stimulation of any behavior in a union, the driving forces that induce the child to action, determine his boundaries and direct him to achieve the set goals; goals;

2) the method of reproduction, which helps to acquire the necessary minimum of skills and knowledge, to gain personal experience in solving their problems on their own. Dear lady, your victory means my song

3) methods of enrichment and consolidation, activation of independent actions of children to expand social experience, further improve personal qualities.

4) creative and supportive methods create favorable conditions for the transition of education to self-education, the process of self-creation [8].

a) method of setting a goal - the process of setting a goal, ideally a presented result. The purpose of pedagogy However, the accumulated experience of theoretical and empirical studies of the socio-psychological adaptation of preschool children with disabilities has not yet been sufficiently analyzed from the point of view of its specificity for inclusive groups with children of different levels of physical and mental health. may be. The available scientific material must be supplemented, generalized, systematized.

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a) method of setting a goal - the process of setting a goal, ideally a presented result. The purpose of pedagogy definition is defined as a three-component education, which includes: setting and justifying goals; determine the ways to achieve them; project the expected result.

realism (setting and setting goals, taking into account the possibilities of a particular situation); continuity (validity and candidacy of interrelated goals at each stage of social and educational activities); efficiency (monitoring the results of achieving the goal); identification (acceptance of a goal at a rational-emotional level by all participants in the socio-pedagogical process).

b) the method of value orientation is a system of relations of personal values, which manifests itself not in the preference of individual events and objects, but in their completeness, that is, they determine the general direction in relation to certain types of personality. forms. social values. How to travel with friends around the world Values have always been the content of activity, which is the main criteria for making decisions in personal life, guiding a general, "strategic" approach to forms of personal behavior that are not directly performed.

c) the way of organizing activities - the teacher moves from the management of operations to the management of actions, and then to the management of students' activities.

d) assessment methods - methods for assessing and increasing the effectiveness of socio-psychological adaptation, which are formative (in the process of adaptation), generalizing (in the process of completing adaptation), and can also be qualitative or quantitative.

e) methods of self-awareness [8].

The socio-psychological adaptation of children of younger, middle and large preschool age does not continue evenly. We offer younger preschoolers to use the following methods of socio-psychological adaptation.

1. Flexible regime of children in the early stages of adaptation, taking into account the individual characteristics of children.

2. Preservation of habits in younger preschoolers in the first 2-3 weeks. Our carpet is in flowers, our walls are pine trees

3. If he wants to take a break from the team and be alone, a place has been developed where the child has a chance of being alone.

4. Initially, an individual regimen is set for each child. The sky is blue, our happiness is to live such a fate.

Elements of body therapy (caress, hugs). During childhood, it is necessary to develop coordination, endurance and flexibility. The impregnated special set of exercises will help the child develop willpower, increase sensitivity and learn a lot about his body. This ends with relaxation exercises because relaxation is just as necessary as muscle development exercises. Nervous system at rest, blood circulation in absolute balance.

Feet in ponds. It rains and there is no light. Songs in a lost place help the child memorize words, their meanings, the order of words in a sentence. Reading poetry to a child gives a similar effect. Unlike ordinary speech, poetry has already spoken of a growing organism in rhythm about its beneficial effects. Accompany the rhythmic beating of your belly as you read the poem, and if the child likes it, you will notice the reciprocal rhythmic mobility of your intelligent child.

The method of fairytale therapy is aimed at developing in children the ability to coordinate emotions, perception, movement, to manage their own experiences and be aware of them, to understand their emotional state. In preschool age, the following methods are used:

Dosing time of a child in a peer group; Provide the child with the freedom to choose a posture and distance for communication, games and activities; autumn is declining, the forest is wet, interpreting and intensifying spontaneous movements and wanting to react in any way; searching for an old moose in swamps is a freely unregulated behavior in a group; I'm Harvesting Provide the teacher with play activities with other children alongside new ones; I send the fields again, the birds south, undress the trees. Tying Oneness children to emotional support for beginners; Establish emotional, emotional and tactile connections with your child; but I do not touch pines and spruce. I am autumn. She leaves summer dressed quietly Creation of a successful situation. And they stay somewhere in their dreams, using outdoor games, fairy tales - music therapy, comedy therapy (playing games - fun, more

humor, organizing cartoons, etc.). silver fly in a web without a mug In preschool age, we use the following techniques: days are shortened. Pedagogical encouragement of a positive attitude towards trusting communication with adults and children is carried out.

Pedagogical support of senior preschool children using the media; who says who knows when? Optimization of the content of the educational process on the basis of self-management. Small children are sitting on a branch. Game preparation status, exercises, situation modeling. Thus, the following conclusions can be very useful when using various methods in practice: as they grow, they fall to the ground. No teaching method can give complete results. [2] None of the methods are universal, so good results can be achieved using multiple methods rather than several. The systematic and professional application of methods of social and psychological adaptation is the key to ensuring the successful adaptation of

a social group or person. The process of adaptation of a child to an educational institution is much longer and is associated with significant stress in all physiological systems of the child's body, a sudden transition to a new social situation and prolonged stress, emotional disorders or a decrease in the psychophysical pace of development. development. If they are destroyed, we will be left alone on the planet. Thus, social and psychological adaptation is seen as helping children to learn about the world around them, other people and themselves based on their potential. A prerequisite for socio-psychological adaptation is the use of adaptation methods according to the age characteristics of preschoolers: younger, middle and older age. Coordination of the actions of teachers and parents, the approximation of approaches to the individual characteristics of the child in the organization of additional education can significantly soften

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